

SHAPE DISTORTION ANALYSIS OF A COMPLEX SHAPED WING SKIN SECTION

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ABSTRACT

In the Clean Sky program SFWA (Smart Fixed Wing Aircraft) [1], which is a major European research program, the main objective is to develop an all-new low drag wing. This wing is aimed to significantly reduce fuel consumption and thereby contribute to a greener environment. The Clean Sky program is an important stepping stone to be able to reach the goals of the ambitious ACARE (Advisory Council for Aeronautics Research in Europe) targets.

To meet the goals, a substantial part of the wing must have laminar air flow to reduce total drag of the aircraft. To achieve these goals Saab has developed a co-cured fully integrated carbon fibre upper wing-cover, including leading edge, skin, stringers and rib-feet. This complex structure highlights the needs for accurate shape distortion analysis and tool compensation, to be able to handle global distortion and local waviness of the wing during curing.

Since the upper wing-cover contains more than 100 co-cured structural elements there was a great challenge to deal with this assembled structure both from an analysis point of view, and from a manufacturing standpoint.

This paper covers the analysis methodology and tooling technology used, to be able to produce this complex shaped wing demonstrator to the high standard required to meet the goals for the Clean Sky program SFWA. Results from the shape distortion analysis as well as the design and manufacturing concept of the final wing skin structure are demonstrated.

1. INTRODUCTION

In new aircraft programs like the Airbus A350XWB and Boeing 787 the composite content has increased to 50-60%. To be competitive in the future with the high demands on integration and short lead times there is an increased need for enhanced and harmonised data flow between disciplines in the design chain, such as geometry, tooling, production, measurements and stress office. Due to the increased complexity of the structures, tool compensation becomes more and more important. Today, tool compensations are based on rules of thumb or Finite Element analysis (FE-analysis) on isolated parts, in combination with production trials, which works very well for simple geometries. However, shape distortions of a complex integrated geometry contain both local and global phenomena such as global spring-in, local waviness and global twist. For that reason, refined tools for prediction of shape distortions are an important step towards more efficient development of complex composite articles. In most high performance composites, spring-in is the dominating and most important shape distortion. This, in combination with local stiffness variations within the article, controls the necessary geometry of the tool-set to get a final article within tolerance.

For predictions of shape distortions a linear elastic thermal stress analysis adjusted with information from process trials were used. The advantage with this methodology is a relatively simple

analysis, which requires only basic material data e.g. stiffness properties and coefficients of thermal expansion. Under specific conditions this method is suitable for analysis of complex geometries, [2]. The draw-back is that information from previous articles or a manufacturing trial is needed which makes the analysis sensitive to changes, e.g. the analysis is only valid for the same cure conditions as in the manufacturing trials.

2. SURFACE REQUIREMENTS

To minimize the surface resistance and therefore the drag of an aircraft wing it is crucial to have a smooth surface without dents or steps. By increasing the area of the wing with laminar flow significant savings can be seen on the drag of the aircraft and therefore fuel consumption. Within the Clean Sky Program Saab is developing and manufacturing one out of two concepts on laminar flow upper wing skins.

To achieve this low drag wing, Saab has developed a co-cured fully integrated carbon fibre upper wing-cover, including leading edge, skin, stringers and rib-feet. The goal with this complex structure is to develop and manufacture an upper cover wing skin without gaps, steps or bolts through the aerodynamic surface. This complex structure highlights the needs for accurate shape distortion analysis and tool compensation, to be able to handle global profile distortion and local waviness of the skin surface during curing.

3. DEVELOPMENT TEST PANELS

Two types of test panels, labelled Test panel 1 and Test panel 2 were manufactured to validate the design and manufacturing concept. These test panels were chosen for their representative shape and complexity with respect to the main wing skin. A schematic representation of the two test sections positioning on the wing are presented in Figure 1, and the manufactured Test panel 1 is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the geometry covered by Test panel 1 and 2

Test panel 1 was developed to verify the tooling concept in a cost and time efficient manner. The tooling was manufactured according to nominal geometry and was not compensated for spring back behaviour. The skin was manufactured on a carbon fiber tool surface and the inner tooling was made out of aluminum. The final shape of the panel was measured and compared to the output from the shape distortion analysis. Consequently there was no CAD-geometry to compare the measured results with.

Figure 2: Manufactured Test panel 1

The result was very promising. The rib-feet positioning were very good and the overall quality of the panel made us confident that the chosen tool concept for the skin, stringers and rib-feet was broadly correct.

The evaluation of the waviness was complicated as no nominal surface was available to compare with. Also, the results were difficult to interpret as the tooling surface turned out to be less rigid than expected. Analysing the measured panel and the FE results shows waviness with amplitude of 0.2 mm and a wavelength of 200 mm.

To further validate the manufacturing and simulation concept, and to obtain component test specimens, an additional test panel, denoted Test panel 2, was manufactured. This panel consist of a curved section of the skin, three stringers and three rib-feet. The geometry of the panel is presented in Figure 3.

Test panel 2 was manufactured on an Invar skin mould, with the same ancillary tooling concept and based on experience gained from the tooling of Test panel 1. The skin mould material was changed to Invar to address the problem with deformations of the tool surface, seen on the previous test panel. The tooling for Test panel 2 was fully compensated for spring back to obtain an article with nominal shape. To investigate the spanwise influence of the rib-feet, regarding local waviness, one out of three rib-feet tool compensations on the skin was removed.

Figure 3: The geometry and dimensions of Test Panel 2

3.1 Shape distortion analyses

For Test panel 1, a detailed Finite Element (FE) shape distortion analysis was performed on the nominal CAD-geometry. The result from the analysis was evaluated against the measured shape of the manufactured panel. This was done as a pre-study before the full FE analysis of the tool shape for the 9 metre wing skin was conducted.

A comparison of the global shape shows a good correlation between the measured and calculated results. Maximum global deformation was roughly 80 mm, on both left and right sides. Chordwise facets could be seen on the skin, see Figure 4. Measurements of global shape of Test panel 1, compared to FE-analysis result is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4: Calculated deformation due to shape distortion of Test panel 1

Figure 5: Measurements of Test panel 1, compared to FE-analysis result

For Test panel 2, a detailed FE shape distortion analysis was performed on the nominal CAD-geometry, in the same way as for Test Panel 1. The result from the analysis was used to create the tool surface and the measured shape of the manufactured panel was evaluated against the nominal CAD geometry.

The FE model is shown in Figure 6. The result illustrates the required tool surface. Please note that the deformations are magnified 20 times. The tool surface is still concave but the magnification turns the surface in Figure 6 convex.

Figure 6: Simulation result, Test panel 2

The deformation can once again be divided into global and local deformation. The global out of plane deformation caused by the shape distortion of the curved skin laminate is exaggerated by the stringer laminates causing faceting of the outer surface, giving a total out of plane deformation of 7 mm (from min to max). This global deformation is presented in Figure 6. In addition to this global deformation, a local waviness, stringer to stringer and rib-feet to rib-feet, with a height of ~ 0.1 mm and a wave length of ~ 200 mm can be seen, Figure 7.

Figure 7: Enlarged picture showing local waviness in spanwise direction

3.2 Measurements

For test panel 2, three reference points were defined in the CAD geometry to ensure accurate and consistent measurements of the test panel, see Figure 8. These points were transferred to the panels by marks in the tool surface, and used as nodes in the simulation model where the boundary conditions are applied.

Figure 8: Boundary conditions and reference points

The shape of the panel was measured with the GOM Atos Triple scan MV700 system. The measurements were compared to nominal article shape. The panel was within 0.4 mm in out of plane deformation compared to nominal profile shape, see Figure 9.

Figure 9: Measurement Test panel 2

The tool surface of Test panel 2 was compensated to avoid waviness in accordance with the result from the shape distortion analysis and the observations and experience from Test Panel 1.

The results from the waviness measurements on the manufactured panel are shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Waviness deformation of Test Panel 2

The results show significantly lowered amplitudes of the local waviness with a reduction by 50% as compared to the uncompensated Test panel 1.

3.3 Evaluation and summary of Test panels

For Test panel 1, the results regarding geometric dimensioning and tolerances, the accuracy of positioning of the stringers, rib-feet and spar cap turned out to be very good. The spring back analysis was very close to actual shape which was promising.

The evaluation of the waviness was complicated as no nominal surface to compare with was available. A local waviness was identified in some areas with maximum amplitude of 0.2 mm and a wave length of 200 mm.

For Test panel 2, the global deformations of the panel were ~7 mm (from min to max). This is mainly due to spring in effects caused by the stringers. This induced a faceting on the skin in chordwise direction.

The local deformations within the panel, i.e. waviness, were well within tolerance. The amplitude of the waviness in chordwise direction was ~0.1 mm and the amplitude of the waviness in spanwise direction was ~0.07 mm, with a wavelength of 200 mm. The faceting on the skin in the spanwise direction due to the rib-feet spring in was less than the tolerances specified within the program, even if the tool surface, for one out of three rib-feet, was not compensated for spanwise waviness.

4. MAIN WING SKIN

4.1 General

To simulate the complex shape of all tool surfaces needed to manufacture the fully integrated wing skin, with a wing span of 9 metre, a detailed FE-simulation was performed, taking into account all experience gained from Test panel 1 and Test panel 2. By using the same material-, simulation- and tool- concept for the main wing skin as for the test panels, a high degree of confidence is built up to obtain an article that will fulfil the challenging shape requirement specified within the Clean Sky program SFWA, [1].

4.2 Analysis model

The complete FE-model of the wing skin contains 284941 quadratic hexahedral layered solid elements, 1767030 nodes and in totals 100 parts. Abaqus Tie constraint was used to merge the different parts together and a total of 241 constraints were applied within the model. The model is shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Wing Skin FE-Model

Boundary conditions were applied in three nodes to prevent rigid body motion. These points were transferred from the tool surface onto the final article. The boundary conditions are shown in Figure 12. The numbers indicate the degree of freedom locked in each location, i.e. 1,2,3 indicates that the panel was constrained in x-, y-, and z-direction.

Figure 12: Boundary conditions

4.2.1 Result from shape distortion analysis

The maximum and minimum deformation was 21 mm and -19 mm respectively, see Figure 13.

Figure 13: Deformation shape for the wing panel, magnified 40 times

As for Test panel 1 and 2, waviness can be seen, both in chordwise and spanwise direction, see Figure 14. The waviness was in the same order, ~ 0.15 mm, as seen on the smaller panels.

Figure 14: Skin waviness, shown without rib-feet

4.3 Tool concept

After simulation of all the different tool surfaces, regarding skin, stringers and rib-feet a significant number of tools were manufactured. The tooling material for all full length tools, spanning over the full 9 metres was chosen to be Invar, with the largest one being the main skin tool weighing in at over 5500 kg. The shorter tools needed to complete the inner tool-set, including 73 boxes, were made out of

aluminium.

The skin is initially laid-up on an aluminium male tool utilising the ATL (Automated Tape Laying) machine. The skin is then turned in to position in the female Invar tool, see Figure 15 and Figure 16. All stringers and rib-feet are then laid-up on separate tools and carefully positioned on to the skin. The CAD geometry for the inner tool assembly used to support stringers and rib-feet are presented in Figure 17.

Figure 15: Main wing skin Invar tool

Figure 16: ATL-tool docking into the Main skin tool

Figure 17: CAD geometry of the inner tool set

5. CONCLUSIONS

An extensive work regarding shape distortion analysis and tooling of a low drag upper wing skin, has been performed as part of the SFWA project within the Clean Sky Program. The work consisted of more than 100 parts that needed to be analysed and appropriate tools were manufactured.

A building block approach was used, where a number of test panels were manufactured and measured to verify the tooling concept and analysis methodology, leading to the final design chosen for the full 9 metre wing skin.

Regarding results from the shape distortion analysis, a similar behaviour could be seen for the test panels as for the main wing skin regarding global bending and twist. For Test panel 1, a global faceting due to the stringers were observed and a local waviness was identified in some areas with maximum amplitude of 0.2 mm.

For Test panel 2, where the tool surface was shape compensated, the global faceting and the local waviness was successfully reduced. The global and local deformations, for all panels, were found to behave in a predictable and similar manner. For Test panel 2 the manufactured panel was well within the tolerances specified within the project.

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